

USE OF MULTIPLE CORES IN CSOUND

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The basic concepts and the new algorithms that are used in Csound6 in order to enhance performance via parallelism are described in some detail. The hope is that this will assist users in determining when this technology is advantageous, and in how to write instruments that are suited to this level of parallelism. The paper ends with a short consideration of how the scheme could be improved.

1 Background

For many years we were used to computers getting faster. Moore's "Law", that the number of transistors on a chip doubled every 18 months, has held and was used to increase the clock speed of processors. However increasing clock speeds requires more power and generates more heat; giving the current 4-5 GHz practical limit. Instead, increasing transistor counts have been used to provide multiple cores.

With the change in hardware developments from faster clock speeds it is imperative that the audio computing community, and the Csound community in particular, determine how they can make best use this change.

This paper is a presentation of the thoughts and experiments in which we have been involved, and especially the second Csound design. The first design has been reported in [1, 2] but its performance was not as good as was hoped.

Many years ago one of us worked with Robert S. Barton, one the greats of early computing, who said there is a *technological imperative*; what hardware requires is a forcing term on software. The project was to design and build a massively parallel computer, but in common with many other attempts at parallelism at that time it did not succeed; but we can learn from the experience.

The philosophical position that we take in this work may be controversial but;

- there must be **no semantic change** in the Csound orchestra language;

- there should be **no user changes** necessary to use.

The first of these is helped by the clear and stated rule that instruments are evaluated in ascending numeric order and that directs our model.

The second may seem pessimistic or even rude, but it is driven by the observation that Csound users are not (typically) software experts and will get it even more wrong than the experts do. Users cannot be expected (or trusted) to modify their thinking for parallel execution, and the responsibility needs to be taken by the software translation system that converts the program or specification into an executable form.

2 Overall Design

The design was based on work at University of Utah by Marti [8, 7] on parallel LISP, and later developed at the RAND Corporation by him for application to TimeWarp simulation.

The model has two components, determining what can be run in parallel and arranging a task dispatcher to observe the semantics.

3 Compilation Time

The granularity of the parallelism is the instrument. The observation at the heart of the method is that two instrument instances can be run simultaneously if they do not access the same (global) entity, and at least one of them writes to it. That is just reading is benign, but changing it requires the numerical sequence must be maintained.

The parser can be used to identify the uses of global values by an instrument as part of the semantic pass over the parse tree. At compile time we construct sets for each function of read locations, written locations and read-write locations. From these sets we will be able to control the parallel dispatch at run time.

In Csound the i-, p-, k-, a-, and f- variables are all local to the instrument instance and so cannot cause any conflicts. Thus they can be ignored in the analysis. But all global variables may be a cause of conflict. It is these we identify.

It should be noted that there are also other global entities we will consider later; tables, zak, and channels as well as the deprecated stack opcodes and all printing.

3.1 Compiler Example

To illustrate this in a simple way consider the instruments

```
instr 1
  a1 oscil p4, p5, 1
  out a1
endin
instr 2
  gk oscil p4, p5, 1
endin
```

```
instr 3
  a1 oscil gk, p5, 1
  out a1
endin
```

Clearly instrument 1 is devoid of global variables and as such can be run independently of any other instrument. Instrument 2 writes to a global variable which is read by instrument 3. So all instrument 2 instances must run before instrument 3. To maintain the semantics multiple instances of instrument 2 need to be serialised as well. This is shown in figure 1.

Figure 1 Partial Ordering from Analysis

3.2 Improvements

The analysis above only relates to global variables, where it is easy to identify them from the parse tree. But the “hidden” globals need more care.

First of there in found in the out family of opcodes which write to an internal hidden global — the spout vector. It would be possible to insert this dependency at parse-time but this would tend to serialise too much. We note that these opcodes always add into a value, and so order does not matter, so long as it is not running in parallel¹. What does matter of course is that each write must be indivisible, and this can be done easily with the insertion of a simple spin-lock in the sources of all of the out family of opcodes.

The other main collection of unidentified global entities are tables, zak scratch area and the various channels and busses. So the parser can note these a significant change had to be made to the OENTRY structure so each opcode is required to declare in this structure what facilities it uses in reading and writing to these global entities, via a field of bit-patterns. For example look at the third field in

```

...
{ "oscilli", S(OSCIL1), TR, 3, "k", "ikij", ...
{ "tableiw", S(TABL), TW, 1, "", "iiiooo", ...

```

¹This is not strictly true as with floating point values rounding errors will be different with different orders. We believe that these differences are unlikely to be audible; partial experiments bear this out.

```

{ "zkr", S(ZKR), ZR, 3, "k", "k", ...
{ "zkw", S(ZKW), ZW, 3, "", "kk", ...
{ "chani", 0xFFFF, CR, 0, NULL, NULL, ...
{ "chano", 0xFFFD, CW, 0, NULL, NULL, ...
...

```

where the codes are for table, zak and channel read and write. Of course this is pessimistic as access to any table is noted rather than conflicting access to the same table, and all zak space is considered one. However it is correct.

Another place where improvements can be made is characterised by the way reverberation is usually done, by adding signals to a global variable which is given to a reverberation opcode in a high-numbered instrument. This will lead to serialising all instruments. A similar concept as in the out opcodes applies; adding into a global is mainly order independent. With the introduction of += syntax it is relatively straightforward to insert a spinlock round the adding in. With a small user adjustment to use the new syntax provides a big saving.

4 RunTime

The idea is to identify at compilation time functions (instruments) that do not have conflict, and to construct a directed acyclic graph (DAG) of dependency which is used at runtime to inform the multiple dispatch. Here we are breaking new ground as the previous uses of this approach did not address this in detail [4, 3].

In Csound5's parallelism [9] maintaining the DAG was a major problem. It is consumed on each k-cycle, and so it had to be reconstructed or copied frequently, involving memory allocation. As a result it only delivered moderate performance gains if at all.

For Csound 6 we developed a different idea, where semantic analysis is used to inform and the creation of the DAG of dependencies only on instantiation/termination of instrument-instances. This greatly reduces memory activity, but it needs a very different approach.

The inspiration comes from the lazy data structures used in modern SAT solvers [6]. This gives two key ideas:

- An instrument can only be run when *all* instructions preceding it in the DAG have been run. Thus it is sufficient to monitor ('watch') the state of one predecessor and only consider the others when it has been run.
- When an instrument finishes, all of the instruments that are watching it are moved to watch an other of their predecessors, if there are any that have not been run, or, if all have been run, it is marked as runnable. Threads needing work do not need to check dependencies.

This can be written without dynamic memory allocation, with fixed data size. Also it is lock-free, with few mutexes and only two race cases. And importantly only for new instrument instances or ending instances does the structure need remaking.

There are three major data structures:

- A vector indexed by the task number which records the current state of the task. A task can be in one of four states; **WAITING** for some other task(s) to finish, **AVAILABLE** when all dependencies have been met, **INPROGRESS** while it is running and **DONE** when it is finished;
- A vector of sets of tasks to maintain the static dependences of a task, build from the compilation data;
- A vector of lists of tasks that are currently waiting for each task to complete, called the watch-list. It is worth noting that the watch-list says who is watching me, not who I am watching.

These are illustrated in figure 4. It may appear that maintaining the watch-lists requires memory, but in the very worst case each task may be watching one other, so the list elements cannot exceed the number of tasks, and so it can be pre-allocated, via a memory manager.

Figure 2 Major data structures

If a thread wants work to do it only needs to search the task status vector for an **AVAILABLE** task. If this is done with an atomic compare-and-swap primitive to set it to **INPROGRESS** then there is no need to lock the search. Such a primitive is provided in the gcc compiler.

If the search fails to find an **AVAILABLE** task then either all tasks are **DONE** and the control cycle has ended, or there is still **INPROGRESS** tasks and we can loop. This seeking a task is described as:

```
for (i=0; i<num_of_tasks; i++) {
    if (__sync_bool_compare_and_swap(&(task_status[i]),
                                     AVAILABLE, INPROGRESS)) {
        return (taskID)i;
    }
    else if (ATOMIC_READ(task_status[i])==DONE) {
        donework++;
    }
}
if (donework==num_of_tasks) return (taskID)FINISED;
```

```
return (taskID)WAIT;
```

When a task finishes it first needs to change its own status to `DONE` and then walk its watchlist. Each watcher is moved to an unfinished dependent task’s watch-list, or the watcher is marked as `AVAILABLE`.

There are two potential race cases in accessing the watch list: two threads could try to add different tasks to the same watch list or a task could try to add to a watch list as it is being emptied. The first is handled by using compare-and-swap to perform lock-free insertion into a single linked list. The second is resolved by having a ‘block’ value, which the stops insertion. When a thread wishes to empty the list, it atomically swaps in the block value and takes exclusive ownership of the list.

5 Results

In table 1 we show the relative performance with multiple threads in three well-known existing Csound code examples, `-j` indicates the number of threads used. This was run on a 4-core Intel i7 processor. Clearly for both *CloudStrata* and *Xanadu* the performance is good and there is a small improvement with larger `ksmps`. Three-fold speed up with 4 cores is much better than was achieved in the Csound5 model. The case of *Trapped in Convert* is less good, with very little improvement from 1 to 2 cores. This is because inadvertently this example is full of details that slow the system down. This is covered in section 6.

This is coarse grain parallelism, and performs better with “heavy” instruments. Larger values of `ksmps` tend to increase the improvements, as does few cross instrument dependencies.

-j	CloudStrata	Xanadu		Trapped...		
	ksmps=500 (sr=96000)	ksmps=10	ksmps=100	ksmps=10	ksmps=100	ksmps=1000
1	1	1	1	1	1	1
2	0.54	0.57	0.55	0.75	0.79	0.78
3	0.39	0.40	0.40	0.66	0.76	0.73
4	0.32	0.39	0.33	0.61	0.72	0.70

Table 1 Relative times for processor number and `ksmps`

6 Implications for System and User

The system could be improved by tracking the actual table or channel used, and hence removing some pessimistic constraints. Unfortunately this requires a deal of code as well as more opcode annotation to indicate which argument is a table *etc.*

The original philosophy is that the user need do nothing; but a few simple changes should increase the utility of multiple cores. As we prefer heavy instruments and large `k-cycles` we would encourage users to set `sample-accurate` and use larger `ksmps` than commonly used, together with using `a-rate` envelopes and parameters. This make for longer computations before task switches.

Similarly incorporating the use of += and -= syntax where appropriate way increase the amount of parallelism found. This applies significantly to reverberation and other global effects, but is generally true.

In order to assist with what is meant by a heavy instrument it would be good to collect more data on opcode costs to see if there are ways of predicting performance. There is an initial data collection [5, 2] but it needs to be extended.

We have a couple of algorithm improvements which might give a small improvement but they are not yet deployed. The writing of this paper has spurred us to optimise the algorithms.

7 Acknowledgments

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